

SKILLS REQUIRED FOR SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETERS AND PROBLEMS THEY MIGHT ENCOUNTER

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Abstract

This work aims at exploring basic concepts about simultaneous interpretation as well as providing skills required in order to be a good interpreter. It gives a lot of tips to foster interpretation skill. Moreover, it discusses potential problems an interpreter may encounter during translation process.

Keywords: conference interpreting, multilingual communication, ethical conduct, cultural knowledge, listening skills, vocabulary, stress management, cognitive processing.

1.1 Simultaneous Interpretation in general

Multiple types of multinational conferences and conferences often require simultaneous interpreting. Although very difficult, it is one of the most common forms of interpreting. Simultaneous interpreting requires the interpreter to translate what is being said in a time period that matches the speaker's pace and does not alter the natural flow of the conversation. Simultaneous interpretation requires the interpreter to interpret what the speaker is saying while the speaker is speaking. There should be no waiting time between the interpreter and the receipt of what was said. Short pauses are allowed to process the speaker's words. Simultaneous interpretation is often used at the United Nations. Simultaneous interpretation will be provided for the president's speech.

What Is Interpretation?

Language interpreting is the verbal translation of a given speech. An interpreter translates the words spoken in the source language into the intended target language much like a written translation. According to Kemin¹, six types of interpreters are widely used around the world: *simultaneous interpretation, consecutive interpretation, whispering interpretation, on-site interpretation, escort interpretation, telephone interpretation (planned), on-demand telephone interpretation.*

The interpreter's job is to successfully convey all the semantic elements of speech, including tone. The interpreter must also convey the intent of the message the speaker is trying to convey.

Very Demanding Work

In the world of language services, simultaneous interpreting can be classified as one of the most demanding. The interpreter must have excellent language skills and above average two language proficiency. Also, you need to be mentally prepared. Simultaneous interpreting means correctly interpreting what is being said while introducing the necessary nuances into the target language. The environment itself can be stressful. Interpreters cannot look up

¹ Kemin (2004)

unfamiliar expressions or terms in dictionaries. This is a good reason to have good knowledge of the source and target languages. Interpreters must be completely confident in their speaking skills. This job also requires improvisational flair in the interpreter.

Why is It Important?

Language services, such as B. Interpretation, strive to break down language barriers and ensure proper understanding and effective communication. Simultaneous interpretation makes it much easier for participants to quickly understand what the speaker is saying.

Simultaneous interpretation is important for several reasons:

- *Efficient communication provider because it gives representatives an equal opportunity to share their knowledge and ideas. Participants can also listen to speeches in their native language.*
- *This is done in real time so no messages are lost. Participants can easily express their opinions, thoughts and ideas in commonly used languages.*
- *Multilingual meetings are facilitated because this type of interpretation facilitates proper and accurate communication. Participants feel free to communicate in their own language knowing that they can communicate effectively with other delegates.*
- *Simultaneous interpretation avoids the time-consuming task of translating documents and speeches into all participants' languages.*

Accurate service as the interpreter translates the message immediately. Consecutive interpreting relies on the interpreter's notes and memory to get the message across.

The history of simultaneous interpreting

In the literature on the history of interpreting, simultaneous interpreting tended to be associated with the development of conference interpreting, particularly with the Nuremberg Trials after World War II². Undoubtedly, a lot of attention was paid to simultaneous interpreting at the Nuremberg Trials. Simultaneous interpreting has been experimented with by him at the ILO (International Labor Organization) and the League of Nations, with limited success of that scope resistance.

Leading conference interpreters feared the development would damage their reputations and working conditions³. In sign language interpreting, simultaneous interpreting probably became a common interpreting mode, and perhaps an early standard mode. Spoken language interpreting has audio interference between the source language and the interpreter's utterance, whereas sign language interpreting does not. Wolfgang Zieke⁴ reported that Laurent Claire had signed US President James Monroe to the US Senate and Congress as early as 1818, stating that "While he was signing," Henry Hudson, an American teacher, "spoke the word." After World War II, simultaneous interpreting was mainly used in international organizations where rapid interpretation between multiple languages was required and waiting for multiple consecutive interpretations into multiple languages was not an option. However, it soon expanded to other settings such as multinational corporations, especially board meetings, shareholder meetings, briefings, press conferences, international medical, scientific and technical conferences and seminars, and the media. Television interpreting, for example, has

² Nan Xue (2007)

³ Weihe Zhong (2001)

⁴ Wolfgang Zieke (1970)

become perhaps the most visible (most) form of simultaneous interpreting, in both spoken and sign language. There is probably very few people in the world who have access to radio or television who have not encountered numerous simultaneous interpreting opportunities. Professional organizations of conference interpreters such as AIIC (Association of International Conference Interpreters, founded in Paris in 1953 and the most prestigious organization that has shaped much of the professional practice and standards of conference interpreting) are among the major as a high-level simultaneous interpreter, but conference interpreting is beneficial in Simultaneous interpreting, although primarily in whisper form, is also used in courts and various public services. Overall, simultaneous interpreting has become, alongside the ubiquitous sign language interpreting, the primary mode of interpreting at international organizations and multilingual conferences of political, economic, scientific, technical, and other high-level professionals. Consecutive interpreting is strong against conversational interpreting at level legal conferences and TV programs. During individual business negotiations, when visiting overseas personalities, and during on-site meetings where it is difficult to install interpretation equipment.

1.2 The skills and qualities required for being a good interpreter

Interpreting is a highly specialized profession that requires training and practice. A professional-level interpreter acquires many skills that the average bilingual person does not have or is not well-honed. Here are five interpreting qualifications to look for when choosing a quality professional interpreter⁵.

1. Language skills

Most people don't realize how much knowledge and vocabulary an interpreter needs in their native language. Michelle Hof⁶, professional conference interpreter and trainer who runs the blog The Interpreter Diaries, writes:

"As an interpreter, you need to be able to express yourself well in different vocal ranges and have access to a wide active vocabulary that covers different areas. Just because you grew up speaking a language doesn't mean you automatically have those skills. I always see early in the course that students cannot stop talking the same way they talk to their friends at a bar and start sounding like an interpreter."

That is exactly what the native language of the interpreter needs. Her website for the Association of International Conference Interpreters (AIIC) states that in order to become an interpreter, she must "have the same level of language comprehension as an educated native speaker of the same language." increase.

2. Listen and learn

Mainly there are two ways of interpretation; consecutive and simultaneous interpreting. Consecutive interpreting is typical of the healthcare industry. You must wait for the speaker to pause before translating. In this modality, the speaker may speak for several minutes before pausing, requiring active and active listening, memory retrieval, and note-taking in order to make an accurate interpretation.

Interpreting requires more brain power than usual. Scientists conducted experiments on bilingual people and discovered that when people switch between two languages, the brain

⁵ Lamber, (1995)

⁶ Michelle Hof (2005)

uses areas that are not active during normal language use. This suggests that greater coordination of the dynamic manipulation is required, and that phonological processing is more difficult when language switching is required.

3. *Ethical conduct*

Interpreters may come across confidential and confidential information. Those working with healthcare providers must understand the highly regulated environment surrounding patient and consumer privacy. Ethical behavior is more than just remembering what you hear. The U.S. Court's website states that interpreters are impartial and "convey messages accurately and idiomatically from the source language to the recipient language without additions, omissions, or other misleading elements that misrepresent the intended meaning." It is stated that it must be able to convert interpreters who unethically interpret in medical scenarios can affect a doctor's ability to save lives. For this reason, interpreters have a great responsibility and must be dedicated professionals.

4. *Cultural knowledge*

Being bicultural is as important as bilingualism for qualified interpreters. Bicultural individuals naturally absorb the sensitivities and nuances of two cultures and have an innate ability to mediate between them. Holly Mickelson of the Dr. Monterey Institute for International Affairs explains:

"In all their work, interpreters must bridge the cultural and conceptual divides that divide conference participants."

5. *Expertise*

Imagine listening to an academic lecture on aerospace engineering and being asked to review what you have learned unless you are familiar with how aerodynamics work, you may find the lecture difficult to understand.

It is also important that the interpreter understands the subject matter of the conversation he or she has to interpret. In a medical setting, you should be familiar with common medical terms, issues, and procedures. Interpreters who are confused by their lack of expertise may find it difficult to understand what is being said.

1.3. Problems of simultaneous interpretation

Simultaneous interpreting is one of the most difficult forms of interpreting with all kinds of difficulties and disadvantages. As a language student studying to become an interpreter, simultaneous interpreting is still my biggest weakness. Right now, I find it very difficult, if not nearly impossible. I am sure there are many interpreters who share this opinion, so this week I will take a look at some of the factors that make simultaneous interpreting such an intimidating monster.

No Breaks

There are no breaks in simultaneous interpreting. A speaker starts talking and does not stop until he or she has completely finished thinking. This means that the interpreter must maintain the same pace as the speaker throughout the speech. Some speakers recognize that the interpreter needs time to process and gracefully pace what is being said, but of course this is not always the case.

This uninterrupted performance is incredibly disappointing for many. The speakers do not stop, and neither do you. Except for the space between sentences, there is no time to process the speaker's utterances, and in most cases this space is used up by the time you interpret. In a

legal or business setting, she/he may speak for 10 minutes or more before the speaker finishes. Processing and interpreting utterances while preserving the speaker's style, tone, intent, etc. is a challenge in itself, and it takes an incredible amount of energy and energy to do this for an extended period of time, such as 10 minutes. Patience is required. It takes constant effort and training to maintain it and shows how difficult this area is.

High Level of Speech that Must be Transferred to the Target Language

Speaking of special environments, simultaneous interpreting is often done in such places. Legal environments, business meetings, presentations, etc. are some of the most common places for simultaneous interpreting, all of which require highly specialized vocabulary and proficiency.

All of these must be translated accurately into the target language. Combine that with the fact that there are no pauses, and you get a recipe for serious headaches when speakers drop strange jargon you have never heard before. It's not like consecutive interpreting where you have time to ask for clarification and find a solution. You only have a short time to find a suitable equivalent or replacement. Additionally, some fields, such as the legal field, have very specific idioms with very specific equivalents. Many of these fields have very real implications for misinterpretation and put pressure on interpreters to get them right. A lot of preparation at once!

Listening While Speaking

The most difficult part of simultaneous interpretation for me is listening while speaking. That is, the ability to process the speaker while interpreting oneself. For me, this is like breathing in through your mouth and out through your nose. This is completely unintuitive and frustrating, and requires a huge amount of work just to get started. The biggest problem here is the fact that both processes require active thinking and, as we all know, multitasking doesn't work most of the time.

One of these processes has to be simple for simultaneous translation to work. A simultaneous interpreter consciously has to do one thing in order for him to have the freedom to do another. As with decals, this takes a lot of work to achieve, but it can be done in the end. Many of the exercises for improving decal placement apply to this concept as well. For example, you can shadow certain speech while writing down certain things to teach your brain to focus on one thing while another is happening. The most important thing to realize is that this does not come naturally and requires a lot of effort. The sooner you start, the easier it will be!

Conclusion

Simultaneous interpreting is a demanding, challenging, long-term activity that offers many opportunities. It is not only a theoretical knowledge, but also a skill. Therefore, it can be fully mastered only with a lot of practice and practice. Students can only become qualified interpreters by developing perseverance and an awareness of the use of interpreting methods. Therefore, in order to promote social and economic development and achieve the value of English talent, the organization should improve the base of English skills and professional skills, greatly improve the English interpretation skills, and at the same time we need to form an interpreting team.

References:

1. Lamber, S & Moser-Mercer, B. (1995). Bridging the Gap: Empirical research on simultaneous interpreting. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
2. Kemin Fang. (2004). Simultaneous Interpreting Principles and Training. *Journal of Beijing Vocational & Technical Institute of Industry*,7, 72-75.
3. Nan Xue. (2007). Analysis of the Principles of Simultaneous Interpreting. *Journal of Shaanxi Normal University* (Philosophy and Social Sciences Edition)1, 277-279.
4. Weihe Zhong. (2001). Simultaneous Interpreting: Principles and Training. *Chinese Translators Journal*,5, 39-43.
5. Weiwei Zhang. (1999). EC Simultaneous Interpretation. Beijing: China Translation & Publishing Corporation.
6. Wolfgang Zieke. (1970). Conditioning Your Memory. New York: Sterling Publishing Co., Inc.

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